

embed⁺

Bring blended education to the next level

The journey towards EMBED+

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Wiebe Dijkstra

EMBED

2017-2022

A **reference model** for developing
and implementing blended
learning, embracing all levels of
an institution.

European Maturity Model for Blended Education

Implementation guidelines

W.P. Dijkstra & K. Goeman

 Duration
5 weeks

 Weekly study
2 hours

 100% online
How it works

 Unlimited subscription
~~€299.99~~ **€209.99**
for a whole year
[Learn more](#)

Making Blended Education Work

★★★★☆ 4.7 (82 reviews)

7,207 enrolled on this course

 5 weeks

 2 hours per week

 Digital certificate when eligible

 Intermediate level

[Join course](#)

[Find out more](#) about how to join this course

<https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/making-blended-education-work>

Interim Period

2020-2024

A 3D rendering of a COVID-19 virus particle. The virus is depicted as a spherical, textured grey structure with numerous red, crown-like spikes protruding from its surface. The text "COVID-19" is overlaid in large, bold, white, sans-serif capital letters across the center of the virus. The background is dark, with a few small red and orange specks scattered around the virus.

COVID-19

RPnow
POWERED BY SOFTWARE SECURE

TurningPoint

Mentimeter

socrative

padlet

bongo
by YOUSEEU

PROCTOR
EXAMS

1

Adaptation of
educational
technology

2019 - Innovation session

2020 - EADTU Bridging

2020 - EUA 2020 EUROPE...FORUM

2020 - Sefi conference

2020 - SOPochtend

2020 - Vlaamse onderwijsdag

2021 - Course level EDEN

2021 - Deense minister...ucation

2021 - EADTU WEBINAR

2021 - Institution - SURF OWD

2021 - Progra...ntwerpen

2021 - ROCVA

2022 - Aalborg

2022 - Course - HSLeid...& Tilburg

2022 - Course - TU Delf...webinar

2024 - Course - TU Delf...nar copy

2024-06-27 - EMBED...directors

Presentaties Willem

Workshops

1

Adaptation of
educational
technology

2

Adaptation by
institutions of
EMBED

EMBED+

2024 - 2027

EMBED+ Partners

*In this project, the original EMBED-framework will be evaluated, updated, and validated based on a **use and needs analysis** among EMBED-users, a **literature review**, and a **delphi study**.*

This leads to a new model: EMBED+.

*Based on EMBED+, a **digital hub** is developed including resources (e.g., toolkits, digital self-assessment tool, AI-bot) which HEI can use to mature in blended education.*

*The project will be disseminated via **training-events**, an **online community**, **conferences**, and a **closing event**.*

Outcomes of EMBED+

1

**Validated
EMBED+
framework**

2

**Resources
hub & online
community**

3

**Publications,
proceedings
and reports**

EMBED+Model

Defining the blend

Blended learning

learning as a result of a **deliberate, integrated combination** of online and face-to-face learning activities.

Blended teaching

designing and facilitating blended learning activities.

Blended education

the formal context of BL that is determined by **policies and conditions** with regard to the organization and support of blended learning.

Maturity \neq Quality

*“Maturity is a measurement of the ability of a course, programme, or organisation for **continuous improvement** in a particular discipline”*

4 levels of maturity

Level 1: Ad Hoc

Decisions are reactive,
based on individual
preferences.

Data is not used.

Processes are not
standardized

4 levels of maturity

Level 1: Ad Hoc	Level 2: Deliberate
<p>Decisions are reactive, based on individual preferences.</p> <p>Data is not used.</p> <p>Processes are not standardized</p>	<p>Decisions are deliberate and supported by theory, models and/or proven practices.</p> <p>Decision making relies on professional judgment</p> <p>Some processes are standardized</p> <p>Data plays a minimal role</p>

4 levels of maturity

Level 1: Ad Hoc	Level 2: Deliberate	Level 3: Data-informed
<p>Decisions are reactive, based on individual preferences.</p> <p>Data is not used.</p> <p>Processes are not standardized</p>	<p>Decisions are deliberate and supported by theory, models and/or proven practices.</p> <p>Decision making relies on professional judgment</p> <p>Some processes are standardized</p> <p>Data plays a minimal role</p>	<p>Decisions are shaped by data, but human interpretation remain central.</p> <p>Data is actively collected, analysed and used to improve practices</p> <p>Most processes are standardized</p> <p>Data is not yet systematically integrated in all processes and practices.</p>

4 levels of maturity

Level 1: Ad Hoc	Level 2: Deliberate	Level 3: Data-informed	Level 4: Data-driven
<p>Decisions are reactive, based on individual preferences.</p> <p>Data is not used.</p> <p>Processes are not standardized</p>	<p>Decisions are deliberate and supported by theory, models and/or proven practices.</p> <p>Decision making relies on professional judgment</p> <p>Some processes are standardized</p> <p>Data plays a minimal role</p>	<p>Decisions are shaped by data, but human interpretation remain central.</p> <p>Data is actively collected, analysed and used to improve practices</p> <p>Most processes are standardized</p> <p>Data is not yet systematically integrated in all processes and practices.</p>	<p>Reliable data sources and analytical processes are embedded in daily operations,</p> <p>Professional judgment is important but is aligned with robust data insights.</p> <p>Processes are standardized and structurally reviewed.</p> <p>Data is used in a systematic, integrated, and proactive way.</p>

COURSE
LEVEL

PROGRAMME
LEVEL

ORGANISATION
LEVEL

COURSE
LEVEL

PROGRAMME
LEVEL

ORGANISATION
LEVEL

New education building Pulse

<https://www.tudelftcampus.nl/projects/pulse-2/>

Virtual tour: https://nmc360.tudelft.nl/vt_pulse/

Least squares problems

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ -1 & 1 \\ 2 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{b} = \begin{bmatrix} 10 \\ 8 \\ 7 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Let's go to work!

Assignment

1. Introduce yourself
2. Pick one of the dimensions of the organisation level
3. Go to the corresponding page in this document
4. Study the dimension and its indicators
5. Elaborate your point of view about the maturity level of your organisation
6. Explain what you'd like to change or improve

PS: May there be time left, discuss the next dimension

PSS: Write down anything what is vague, unclear, or could be improved

Assignment

edu.nl/ytn3v

Feedback

edu.nl/qnvnv

Next steps EMBED+

Next Steps

1

**Validated
EMBED+
Framework**

June '26

2

**Resources
hub & online
community**

June '27

3

**Publications,
proceedings
and reports**

Jan '27

www.embedplus.eu